

Implementation of Data Mining as a Decision Support

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Abstract

The phenomenal growth of Android platform in these recent years has made it as a beneficial target among developers of applications. The convenience of Android and its variety of applications which could be produced have caused problems to users in choosing applications suitable for their needs. The decision of categories on Android platform expected to overcome users' problems. On the other hand, selecting categories which would be the basis of producing applications could be an important and difficult matter among developers of applications. For those reasons, this research was aimed to determine the categories of Android applications by using permission. Data Mining Method alongside Permission and Algorithm C4.5 were utilized in this research. The research findings in the form of a decision tree would be utilized in determining the categories of Android applications

Keywords: Data mining, Permission, Decision Tree, Algorithm C4.5, Android applications

1. Introduction

The phenomenal growth of Android platform in these recent years has made it as a beneficial target among developers of applications (Bhaskar, Ninghui, Chris, Rahul and Cristina, 2012). Moreover, the developers should be able to predict some problems occurred. Approaches towards the categorization have been studied thoroughly. The basis of the research was by focusing on the categorization of applications through *permission*. This research focused on the categorization of applications by using *permission* and C4.5 algorithm.

2. Theoretical Basis

Data mining was a process to discover useful information from a big database stored in storage by using pattern recognition technique such as statistics technique, mathematics, artificial intelligence, and machine learning (Meilani dan Slamet, 2013). One of the techniques in data mining was Decision Tree Method. It changed facts into a decision tree which represent the rules. Algorithm for creating a decision tree in this research was Algorithm C4.5. The algorithm formed a decision tree from top to bottom, in which the highest attribute was the roots while the lowest attribute was the leaves. To calculate the gain value of an attribute, the following equation was applied:

$$Gain(S, A) = Entropy(S) - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|S_i|}{|S|} * Entropy(S_i)$$

Explanation :

S : Group of Cases

A : Attribute

n : Total partition of attribute A

|S_i| : Total cases in the 1st partition

|S| : Total cases in S

The calculation of entropy could be seen in the following equation.

$$Entropy(S) = \sum_{i=1}^n - p_i * \log_2 p_i$$

Keterangan :

S : Group of cases

n : Total partition S

p_i : Proportion from S_i to S

3. Research Method

The phase of the approach in this research consisted of three phases: **Preparation Phase**, **Pre-Processing Phase**, and **Post-**

Processing Phase. The following was the research path which is going to be discussed in this research. The path could be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Path of the Research Approach

Figure 1 presented the processes in the research. The initial process was Preparation Phase in which the data was prepared, including the search of APK Android files, categories decision, and permission decision which would be utilized to create a decision tree. The next process was Pre-Processing Phase, in which APK files would be extracted by using Advanced Permission Manager. The research table was presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Research Table

4. Discussion

Generally, the formation of a decision tree in algorithm C4.5 was presented as follows (Kusrini, 2009):

- a. Select an attribute as the roots
- b. Make branches for each value
- c. Distribute cases to each branch
- d. Repeat the process until all cases on each branch have the same class. Selection of the attributes as roots is based on the highest gain value from existed attributes.

The calculation was carried out by using algorithm C4.5 to determine the categories of Android applications. The research was conducted using 219 *permissions*, engaging 20 categories and 500 samples of APK files to be tested. Filling of node calculation table

utilized total *permission* in each category. Attribute *Yes* in node calculation table indicated that each sample of the application had *permission* in each category. Attribute *No* was total permission which did not exist in each sample of application in that category. Pay attention to Figure 3.

NODE		JUMLAH KASUS	SOSIAL	GAYA HIDUP	FOTOGRAFI	HIBURAN	PETA&NAVIGASI	PRODUKTIVITAS	KOMUNIKASI	BERITA&MAJALAH	BELANJA	ALAT	KEUANGAN
ACCESS_FINE_LOCATION	YES	250	17	21	11	4	25	4	16	15	20	8	17
	NO	250	8	4	14	21	0	21	9	10	5	17	8

Figure 3 Filling of Node Calculation Table

The next step after node calculation table has been filled with total cases were calculating entropy from all cases based on categories of applications and calculating *Gain* for each attribute. Total Rows of entropy column was calculated by using the entropy equation as the following:

$$Entropy(Total) = \left(-\frac{25}{500} * \log_2\left(\frac{25}{500}\right)\right) + \left(-\frac{25}{25} * \log_2\left(\frac{25}{25}\right)\right) + \left(-\frac{25}{25} * \log_2\left(\frac{25}{25}\right)\right)$$

Entropy(Total)= 4.321928

Entropy for total cases was 4.321928 which would be the roots of the formula to calculate *Gain*. Previously, the entropy was calculated from each tested *permission*. In this case, if the formula had been formulated in excel, it could be dragged from the top row to the bottom so that the entropy would appear. The calculation of *Gain* value in permission rowsutilized the following equation:

$$Gain(Total, Access Fine Location) = 4.321928 - \left(\frac{250}{500} * 4.129502\right) + \left(\frac{250}{500} * 0\right)$$

Gain(Total, Access Fine Location) = 2.2571772

The above calculation was one of the examples to calculate *Gain* value in which Access_Fine_Locationwas the attribute. *The gain* value would be calculated in each *permission* which was adjusted to entropy value in each *permission*. When the calculation was complete, the next step was finding the highest *Gain* value and *permission* with the highest *Gain* value. These would be the root or initial node in the research. If all entropy values were completed, *Gain* value would be calculated and decided. If all *Gains* on node calculation table have been calculated, the highest *Gain* was decided to be the root node. By these results, the provisional decision tree was created before continuing to the next step. It was presented in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4 Decision Tree of Node 1

When node 1 had been calculated, and root node had been decided, the next step was calculating total cases for decision based on attribute permission which had not been decided. This would be branch attribute. In the column of permission and category, the root node would be adjusted as well by using *true* and *false* equation. The equation applied if the application had permission which was symbolized by 1 and the root node had 1 as well. That condition considered the application had *true* value. However, if it did not have permission or symbolized by 0, the application was *false*. The formula to calculate this node was the same as the previous calculation. The difference was that the total cases decreased in accordance with obtained root-node.

In the calculation of node 1.1. and node 1.2, the filling of the research table was adjusted to instructions which had been explained. Consequently, the research continued to the calculation of node 1.1.1 and node 1.1.2. Node 1.1.2 would be calculated by using permission **Access_Fine_Location-Yes** and **Receive_Boot_Complete-No** as the root node. It was the same as the previous calculation. However, the total cases were different. The calculation result of entropy value and gain for node 1.1.2, in which Permission **Get_Account** had the highest value 4,205 and turned the permission into one of branches nodes. As a result, the calculation of node 1.1.2 resulted in attribute **Yes** in Shopping category and **No** in the Lifestyle category.

The next step was doing the calculation for node 1.1.3, with attribute permission **Access_Fine_Location-No** and **Camera-No**. When the calculation table of node 1.1.3 was completed, the following step was calculating entropy and gain to decide the highest gain value. The total cases would be decreased since it was adjusted to the total cases in permission **Record_Audio** which had been processed in the calculation of node 1.1.1. Root node which would be further tested were **Access_Fine_Location-Yes**, **Receive_Boot_Complete-Yes** and **Record_Audio-Yes** with 53 total cases. After further calculation, **PermissionRead_Phone_State** had the highest gain 3.9909, and the entropy for each attribute permission *Yes* and *No* was 0. Therefore, the research finished in node 1.1.1.1. The categories selected in the calculation of node 1.1.1.1 was Entertainment and News & Magazine so that there were 8 categories out of 20 categories resulted in the research. Figure 4.26 was the final decision tree formulated from this research.

Figure 5 Decision Tree of Node 1.1.1.1. Calculation

5. Implementation

The implementation was carried out by testing towards applications listed in the research table. The application which would be tested by searching *permission* existed in its application was MyIM3. The following was the display of permission in the application.

PERMISSION	IMAGE	MANIFEST
Phone calls read phone status and identify android.permission.READ_PHONE_STATE Allows the app to access the phone features of the device. This permission allows the app to determine the phone number and device ID, whether a call is active, and the remote number connected by a call.		
Camera take pictures and videos android.permission.CAMERA Allows the app to take pictures and videos with the camera. This permission allows the app to use the camera at any time without your confirmation.		
Your location precise location (GPS and network-based) android.permission.ACCESS_FINE_LOCATION Allows the app to get your precise location using the Global Positioning System (GPS) or network location sources such as cell towers and Wi-Fi. These location services must be turned on and available to your device for the app to use them. Apps may use this to determine where you are, and may consume additional battery power.		
approximate location (network-based) android.permission.ACCESS_COARSE_LOCATION Allows the app to get your approximate location. This location is derived by location services using network location sources such as cell towers and Wi-Fi.		
Your applications information run at startup android.permission.RECEIVE_BOOT_COMPLETED Allows the app to have itself started as soon as the system has finished booting. This can make it take longer to read the phone and allow the app to slow down the overall phone by always running.		
Camera retrieve running apps android.permission.GET_TASKS Allows the app to retrieve information about currently and recently running tasks. This may allow the app to discover information about which applications are used on the device.		
Your accounts read Google service configuration com.google.android.providers.gsf.permission.READ_GSERVICES Allows this app to read Google service configuration data.		
use accounts on the device android.permission.USE_CREDENTIALS Allows the app to request authentication tokens.		
Affects Battery prevent phone from sleeping android.permission.WAKE_LOCK Allows the app to prevent the phone from going to sleep.		

Figure 6 Extraction from MyIM3 Application

In Figure 6 above, there was some *permission* to be tested for categorization based on a decision tree that had been created. The first step was searching *permission* node as the research root: **Access_Fine_Location**. It was tested whether the application has permission. If *Yes*, the research advanced to searching branches node, if *No*, branches node would be searched as well according to the attribute. It continued until the test showed the application belonged to which category. The test finished in a category which was selected: Personalization. The following Figure 8 was the description of the test path in MyIM3 application.

November 30, 2018

Figure 8 Decision Tree of MyIm3 Application

In the above test, it could be identified that MyIM3 application was included to the category of Personalization. The following figure presented the display on PlayStore. In that marketplace, the application included to Personalization as well (pay attention to Figure 9). It could be concluded that the test was successful.

Figure 9 Category Result From PlayStore

Conclusions

1. Decision tree which was formed from algorithm C4.5 could only create 8 categories on applications out of 20 categories which were tested.
2. Performance of classification rate towards application categories which utilized permission resulted in a good design, even if there were some permission which did not be branched node in the research.
3. The effects toward total data used also affected the accuracy from the data which was tested, therefore, further research about candidate optimization was necessary.

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